

Studies on Some N-Acyl N-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal-complexing Ligands

Nripendra Nath Ghosh and Gautam Siddhanta

Metal complexes with N-*o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamines have been prepared. N-*m*- and *p*-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V) and U(VI) are isolated. But in the case of *o*-nitrobenzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III) and V(V) complexes have been isolated. The magnetic properties of some of the complexes have also been studied. They appear to be high spin complexes.

N-Acyl-N-phenylhydroxylamines are well known as complexing agent^{1,6}. The benzoyl derivative has been widely used in analytical chemistry and the success of this compound has led the present authors to investigate the effect of nitro substitution in *ortho*, *meta* and *para* positions. The reagents have one replaceable hydrogen and they are represented by

Complexes have been isolated with Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Al(III), V(V), U(VI) in the case of R_mH and R_pH , but Cu(II), Fe(III), Al(III) and V(V) complexes are only isolated in the case of R_oH . Titanium complexes could not be isolated in the pure condition in each case.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of N-ortho, meta and para-nitro-benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamines: These were prepared by the addition of the required acid chloride (1 mole) to an aqueous solution

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of phenylhydroxylamine (1.5 moles)⁷. Sodium bicarbonate was added from time to time to keep the mixture faintly alkaline. Both mono- and di-substituted products were formed. The resulting solid was dissolved in ether and the ether layer was extracted with dilute cold ammonia solution. The ammonia extract was just acidified with ice cold dilute H_2SO_4 when white shining crystals of the mono derivative separated. These were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The results of analyses are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	M.P.	% Nitrogen	
			Found	Reqd..
R_mH	White	112°.	10.75	10.85
R_oH	White	144°	10.77	10.85
R_pH	White	158-159°	10.74	10.85

These compounds are stable. They are sparingly soluble in cold water, more soluble in hot water. They are soluble in organic solvents like ethanol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, ether etc. but insoluble in petroleum ether.

Preparation of metal chelates : The procedure followed for preparation of compounds were almost identical except the pH at which complete precipitation took place varied with the nature of the ligand. The general procedure followed is described below.

Copper (II) compounds : To an aqueous solution of copper acetate (1 mole) an ethanolic solution of the reagent (2.2. moles) was added with stirring. The pH was adjusted with dilute ammonia. The compound separated was filtered and washed with water and finally with aqueous ethanol and air dried.

Nickel (II) compounds : To an aqueous solution of nickel acetate (1 mole) an ethanolic solution of the reagent (2.2. moles) was added with stirring. The pH was adjusted with sodium acetate and stirring was continued for about 10 mins. The compound separated was filtered and washed with water, finally with aqueous ethanol and air dried.

Iron (III) compounds : An aqueous solution of ferric chloride (1.1 mole) containing HCl was added to an ethanolic solution of the reagent (3 moles) so that the pH of the mixture would remain <1. A red colour developed. The pH was then raised by dropwise addition of sodium acetate with stirring when a compound separated. It was filtered and washed with aqueous ethanol and air dried.

Aluminium (III) compounds : To an ethanolic solution of the reagent (3.2 moles), an aqueous solution of aluminium nitrate (1 mole) was added with stirring. The pH was raised by addition of sodium acetate when a compound separated. The solution was stirred for a further period of 15 mins. and was allowed to stand for 1 hr. The compound was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and air dried.

Vanadium (V) compounds : To an aqueous solution of sodium vanadate (1 mole) an acetone solution of the reagent (2.2 moles) was added with stirring. The resulting yellow solution was diluted with water to 300 ml and dilute hydrochloric acid was added

dropwise to lower the *pH*. The mixture was kept at 60-70° for 30 mins. The compound separated was filtered and washed with water, finally with aqueous ethanol and air dried.

Uranium (VI) compounds : To an ethanolic solution of the reagent (1.8 moles) an aqueous solution of uranyl acetate (1 mole) was added with stirring. The *pH* was adjusted with sodium acetate. The compound separated was filtered and washed with water till the washings were colourless and air dried.

The compounds were then analysed. Nitrogen was determined by a modified Kjeldahl method.⁸ The magnetic properties of some of the compounds were also studied. They appear to be high spin complexes. Results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Compound with composition	Colour	<i>pH</i> of pptn.	%Nitrogen		%Metal		Magnetic moment (B.M.)
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	
Cu (R _m) ₂	Yellowish green	3.0-3.5	9.87	9.69	10.95	11.00	1.85
Ni (R _m) ₂	Greenish yellow	4.5-5.0	9.85	9.78	10.15	10.26	3.15
Fe (R _m) ₃	Red	1.0-1.5	10.34	10.16	6.79	6.75	5.85
Al (R _m) ₃	White	4.5-5.0	10.48	10.53	3.52	3.38	—
VO(OH)(R _m) ₂	Violet black	1.0-1.5	9.22	9.36	8.51	8.52	Dia
UO ₂ (R _m) ₂	Orange	4.5-5.0	7.19	7.15	29.95	30.36	—
Cu (R _p) ₂	Greenish yellow	3.5-4.0	9.78	9.69	10.72	11.00	1.92
Ni (R _p) ₂	Yellow	4.5-5.0	9.75	9.78	10.31	10.26	3.12
Fe (R _p) ₃	Red	1.0-1.5	10.02	10.16	6.55	6.75	5.90
Al (R _m) ₃	White	4.5-5.0	10.63	10.53	3.35	3.38	—
VO(OH)(R _p) ₂	Violet black	2.0-2.5	9.11	9.36	8.64	8.52	Dia
UO ₂ (R _p) ₂	Orange	4.5-5.0	7.20	7.15	30.11	30.36	—
Cu (R _o) ₂	Green	4.0-4.5	9.86	9.69	10.71	11.00	1.86
Al (R _o) ₃	White	5.0-5.5	10.36	10.53	3.42	3.38	—
Fe (R _o) ₃	Red	1.5-2.0	10.18	10.16	6.86	6.75	5.90
VO(OH)(R _o) ₂	Violet	2.0-2.5	9.48	9.36	8.46	8.52	Dia

Further works with these reagents and on some other N-acyl substituted-N-phenyl-hydroxylamines are in progress.